

SHINING A FORENSIC SPOTLIGHT ON PDF/A

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Abstract – Understanding what preservation formats such as PDF/A (ISO 19005) have “promised” to the preservation community has been influenced by software implementations coupled with certain long-held beliefs and myths about PDF and file formats. In the 20 years since the first PDF/A-1 standard was published, technology, the PDF/A standards, and digital preservation practices have all shifted.

This tutorial aims to shine a forensic spotlight on exactly how the PDF/A file format, and its applications, have evolved to support the reliable, long-term preservation of electronic documents. It aims to separate myth from fact and address certain long-held beliefs that may no longer be true or not be in the best interests of organizations into the future.

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I. INTRODUCTION

ISO 19005 is a series of international standards that define what is commonly known as “PDF/A”, a subset of PDF enabling long-term preservation. Originally envisioned in 2001, PDF/A-1 was first published in 2005 based on Adobe’s PDF 1.4 specification. Most recently, PDF/A-4 has undergone an official ISO dated revision and will be updated in 2025 to support the preservation of PDF 2.0 according to the latest ISO standard for PDF, ISO 32000-2:2020.

The evolution of both PDF technology and preservation practices has resulted in five preservation-centric ISO standards (PDF/A-1, PDF/E-1, PDF/A-2, PDF/A-3, and PDF/A-4) and six

conformance levels (see Table 1: List of PDF ISO standards supporting long-term preservation). In addition, specific industries leverage PDF/A to support their own specific requirements, such as ZUGFeRD and Factur-X for e-invoicing [5], Order-X for e-purchase orders [6], EA-PDF for email archiving [7], and, most recently, a proposed new ruling in the US Financial Data Transparency Act Joint Data Standard to support schema and taxonomy data in US regulated financial reporting [8].

II. CHALLENGES, MYTHS, AND BELIEFS

In the 20 years since PDF/A-1 was first published, the application of PDF/A has established certain beliefs and assumptions. As digital preservation moves forward into an era of new forms of content, AI, and ever increased quantities of data, such concepts should be re-assessed and updated appropriately:

- 1) *“Reliable appearance”*: a key tenant of PDF/A has always been around reliable appearance and “conforming processors”. With new forms of content, such as HDR images from cell phones, interactive 3D, and rich media content, understanding precisely what this means has never been more important.
- 2) *“Under-declared” conformance*: a practice previously driven by software bugs in both PDF creators and PDF validators was the use of “under-declared” conformance levels to pass validation checks. A Well Tagged PDF document with semantically rich information in logical reading order can more easily pass conformance level “B” validation than conformance level “A” or

Table 1: List of PDF ISO standards supporting long-term preservation.

PDF Subset	ISO Standard	Based on PDF version	Conformance Levels
PDF/A-1	ISO 19005-1	Adobe PDF 1.4	A, B
PDF/E-1	ISO 24517-1	Adobe PDF 1.6	n/a
PDF/A-2	ISO 19005-2	ISO 32000-1:2008 (PDF 1.7)	A, B, U
PDF/A-3	ISO 19005-3	ISO 32000-1:2008 (PDF 1.7)	A, B, U
PDF/A-4	ISO 19005-4	ISO 32000-2:2020 incl. Amd.1 (PDF 2.0)	None, F, E

Table 2: PDF version analysis of 1M file corpus - [3]

		Self-identified version								
		1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	2.0
Latest Feature Version	1.0	208	218	1,389	3,232	5,578	372	452	279	-
	1.1	2	656	1,712	10,787	11,797	278	397	5,007	-
	1.2	2	103	1,547	13,599	5,131	4,008	149	14,235	-
	1.3	17	169	2,379	22,998	8,022	645	148	3,034	-
	1.4	18	72	1,351	31,091	154,162	14,691	10,374	79,704	23
	1.5	-	1	276	13,339	59,530	143,205	72,959	90,049	202
	1.6	-	-	32	1,244	26,847	62,120	33,504	62,396	22
	1.7	-	-	11	394	1,610	907	1,695	10,785	-
	2.0	2	10	13	398	829	599	822	1,440	12

Legend	Count	Percent
PDF's stated version equals the latest feature version (<i>diagonal</i>)	367,077	36.9%
PDF's stated version is higher than the latest feature version (<i>above diagonal</i>)	420,889	42.3%
PDF's stated version is lower than the latest feature version (<i>below diagonal</i>)	207,323	20.8%

"U". As a result, and when coupled with previous pragmatic advice from institutions, file submissions may commonly "under-declare" their conformance level to make things easier to pass validation checks but undermine any assumptions about what certain conformance levels may indicate.

- 3) "Over-declared" conformance: in a similar but inverted fashion, PDF/A-3 and PDF/A-4 provided extended support for embedded files of arbitrary format has created opportunities for new applications, include e-finance, engineering and manufacturing, and email archiving. However, there is no mandated requirement that such embedded files must always be present, thus weakening any assumptions about what certain conformance levels may indicate. Pure image PDFs without any text can also technically comply with conformance levels "A" or "U" since these levels are not mandated to contain specific features.

PDF versioning: a long-held belief is that managing digital files necessarily involves managing digital file versions – whether this be PDF, HTML, or other file formats. The underlying assumption in this approach is that each version of a file format introduces new features which might need to be handled or processed in special ways. Although true from a specification document perspective, PDF file versioning accuracy as a reliable indication of contained features has been proven incorrect in more than 20% of files in a 1 million file corpus – see

- 4) Table 2: PDF version analysis of 1M file corpus - [3]. Although this is no different in the way that HTML versioning cannot be relied upon to define which HTML tag set and features are present, the fact that PDF is a binary file format raises far more concerns.
- 5) "Private data": Private data is not a new challenge for preservationists as it exists in many extensible file formats. In the case of PDF/A, private data's influence is well scoped by the ISO

specifications, but its presence still causes many concerns.

- 6) *“Embedded files”*: Software user interfaces have created confusion as to what are “embedded files” in PDF files [2], and this leads to false impressions. Limited implementations, user interface terminology, and software bugs can all reduce visibility of what should be considered an “embedded file” that may require additional attention from archivists.
- 7) *“Searchable PDFs”*: the ability to find PDF documents containing specific information in large repositories has shifted over time. With the application of large-scale document and record management systems and the more recent use of AI, the searchability landscape and reliability of content discovery has changed. Scanned or image-only PDFs that were previously indicated as conformance level “B” (Basic) may now not use any explicit conformance level. Visual LLMs have more capabilities than ever before to discover previously invisible content.

These and other challenges, myths, and beliefs related to PDF/A will be explored forensically, by looking at the ISO specifications alongside example PDF files.

III. CONCLUSION

This tutorial will provide a detailed forensic examination of what the different PDF/A versions and conformance levels enable for long-term preservation. It will look at how the PDF/A standards have evolved over the last 20 years to account for technology changes, new applications, and feedback from stakeholders. It will enable participants to update and align their policy and procedural frameworks with a best practice understanding, both now and into the future.

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Peter Wyatt is the PDF Association’s CTO and has worked with PDF for over 25 years. He is the ISO Project Leader of ISO 32000 (the core PDF standard) and co-chairs the PDF and Imaging Model TWGs. Previously, he was a Principal Investigator on the DARPA “SafeDocs” program, where he developed the Arlington PDF Data Model.

